

New Results of Related-key Attacks on All Py-Family of Stream Ciphers

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Abstract: The stream cipher TPpy has been designed by Biham and Seberry in January 2007 as the strongest member of the Py-family of stream ciphers. At Indocrypt 2007, Sekar, Paul and Preneel showed related-key weaknesses in the Py-family of stream ciphers including the strongest member TPpy. Furthermore, they modified the stream ciphers TPpy and TPy to generate two fast ciphers, namely RCR-32 and RCR-64, in an attempt to rule out all the attacks against the Py-family of stream ciphers. So far there exists no attack on RCR-32 and RCR-64. In this paper, we show that the related-key weaknesses can be still used to construct related-key distinguishing attacks on all Py-family of stream ciphers including the modified versions RCR-32 and RCR-64. Under related keys, we show distinguishing attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64 with data complexity $2^{139.3}$ and advantage greater than 0.5. We also show that the data complexity of the distinguishing attacks on Py-family of stream ciphers proposed by Sekar et al. can be reduced from $2^{193.7}$ to $2^{149.3}$. These results constitute the best attacks on the strongest members of the Py-family of stream ciphers TPpy, RCR-32 and RCR-64. By modifying the key setup algorithm, we propose two new stream ciphers TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 which are derived from RCR-32 and RCR-64 respectively. Based on our security analysis, we conjecture that no attacks lower than brute force are possible on TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 stream ciphers.

Keywords: Cryptanalysis, Related-key Attack, Distinguishing Attack, Py-family of Stream Ciphers, TRCR-32, TRCR-64.

Categories: D.4.6, E.3, K.6.5

1 Introduction

RC4 was designed by Rivest in 1987. It has inspired the design of a number of fast stream ciphers, such as ISAAC [Robert, 96], Py [Biham, 05] and MV3 [Keller, 07]. Being the most widely used software stream cipher, RC4 is extremely simple and efficient. At the time of the invention of RC4, its array based design was completely different from the previous stream ciphers mainly based on linear feedback shift registers.

The stream ciphers Py [Biham, 05] and Py6 [Biham, 05], designed by Biham and Seberry, were submitted to the eSTREAM project for analysis and evaluation in the category of software based stream ciphers. However, due to several cryptanalytic attacks on them [Paul, 06, Crowley, 06], a strengthened version Pypy [Biham, 06] was proposed to rule out those attacks. The ciphers were promoted to the ‘Focus’ ciphers of the Phase II of the eSTREAM project. The impressive speed of the ciphers made them the forerunners in the competition. However, at Eurocrypt 2007, Wu and Preneel showed key recovery attacks against the ciphers Py, Pypy, Py6 with chosen IVs [Wu, 07]. This attack was subsequently improved by Isobe et al. [Isobe, 06]. Distinguishing attacks were reported against Py6 with $2^{68.6}$ data and comparable time by Paul and Preneel [Paul, 06]. These three attacks force the designers to again go for modifications. As a result, three new ciphers TPypy, TPy and TPy6 were built, which can very well be viewed as the strengthened versions of the previous ciphers Py, Pypy and Py6 where the above attacks should not apply [Biham, 07]. Among all the members of the Py-family of stream ciphers, the TPypy is conjectured to be the strongest. The ciphers are normally used with 32-byte keys and 16-byte initial values (or IV). However, the key size may vary from 1 to 256 bytes and the IV from 1 to 64 bytes. The ciphers were claimed by the designers to be free from related-key and distinguishing attacks [Biham, 05, Wu, 07, Biham, 07].

For the analysis of TPypy, TPy and TPy6, several distinguishing attacks have been proposed.

- Sekar, Paul and Preneel published distinguishing attacks on Py, Pypy, TPy and TPypy with data complexities 2^{281} each [Sekar, 07a].
- (at **ISC 2007**). Sekar, Paul and Preneel showed new weaknesses in the stream ciphers TPy and Py [Sekar, 07b]. Exploiting these weaknesses distinguishing attacks on the ciphers are constructed where the best distinguisher requires $2^{68.6}$ data and comparable time.
- (at **WEWoRC 2007**). Sekar, Paul and Preneel mounted distinguishing attacks on TPy6 and Py6 with $2^{224.6}$ data and comparable time each [Sekar, 07c].
- (at **SAC 2007**). Yukiyasu Tsunoo et al. proposed a distinguishing attack on Tpyy that requires 2^{199} words of keystreams [Tsunoo, 07].
- (at **Indocrypt 2007**). Sekar, Paul and Preneel presented related-key distinguishing attacks on TPypy, TPy, Pypy and Py, whose data complexity is $2^{193.7}$ [Sekar, 07d]. Moreover, they have modified Tpyy and TPy to design two new ciphers RCR-32 and RCR-64 which were claimed to be free from all attacks excluding brute force ones.

Compared with other results, the paper [Sekar, 07d] constitutes the best attack on the strongest member of the Py-family of stream ciphers Tpyy. So far there exist no attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64. In this paper, we show that the related-key weaknesses can be still used to construct related-key distinguishing attacks on all Py-family of stream ciphers including the modified versions RCR-32 and RCR-64. Under related keys, we show distinguishing attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64 with data complexity $2^{139.3}$ and advantage greater than 0.5. We also show that the data complexity of the distinguishing attacks on Py-family of stream ciphers proposed by Sekar et al. can be reduced from $2^{193.7}$ to $2^{149.3}$. These results constitute the best attacks on the strongest members of the Py-family of stream ciphers Tpyy, RCR-32 and

RCR-64. By modifying the key setup algorithm, we propose two new stream ciphers TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 which are derived from RCR-32 and RCR-64 respectively. Based on our security analysis, we conjecture that no attacks lower than brute force are possible on TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 stream ciphers.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the structure of all Py-family of stream ciphers is briefly described and the previous related-key attacks are discussed. In Section 3, related-key attacks against RCR-32 and RCR-64 are presented. In Section 4, the improved related-key attacks against Py-family of stream ciphers are presented. Two new stream ciphers TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 are proposed in Section 5. Section 6 concludes this paper.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Brief Description of Py-family of Stream Ciphers

In each of the Py-family of stream ciphers two rolling arrays have been used. One array P is of 256 bytes that contains a permutation of all the values from 0 to 255 and second array Y is an array of size 260 where each word is of 32 bit and is indexed from -3 to 256. Each of the Py-family of stream ciphers is composed of three parts: (1) a key setup algorithm, (2) an IV setup algorithm and (3) a round function or pseudorandom bit generation algorithm (PRBG). The first two parts are used for the initial one-time mixing of the secret key and the IV. These parts generate a pseudorandom internal state composed of (1) a permutation P of 256 elements, (2) a 32-bit array Y of 260 elements and (3) a 32-bit variable s. The key/IV setup uses two intermediate variables: (1) a fixed permutation of 256 elements denoted by *internal_permutation* and (2) a variable *EIV* whose size is equal to that of the *IV*. The round function, which is executed iteratively, is used to update the internal state (i.e., P, Y and s) and to generate pseudorandom output bits. The key setup algorithms of the TPpy, the TPy, the Ppy and the Py are identical. Notation for different parts of the four ciphers is provided in Table 2.

Part	RCR-32	RCR-64	TPpy	TPy	Ppy	Py
Key Setup	<i>KS</i>	<i>KS</i>	<i>KS</i>	<i>KS</i>	<i>KS</i>	<i>KS</i>
IV Setup	<i>IVS₁</i>	<i>IVS₁</i>	<i>IVS₁</i>	<i>IVS₁</i>	<i>IVS₂</i>	<i>IVS₂</i>
Round Function	<i>RF₃</i>	<i>RF₄</i>	<i>RF₁</i>	<i>RF₂</i>	<i>RF₁</i>	<i>RF₂</i>

Table 1: Description of the ciphers RCR-32, RCR-64, TPpy, TPy, Ppy and Py

Due to space constraints, the *KS*, the *IVS₁*, the *IVS₂*, the *RF₁* and the *RF₂*, as mentioned in Table 2, are described in Appendix A. The *RF₃* and *RF₄* are described in Appendix B. The details of the algorithms can also be found in [Biham, 05, Wu, 07, Biham, 07, Sekar, 07d].

In this paper, the notation and the convention followed are described below.

- The outputs generated when key_1 and key_2 are used are denoted by O and Z respectively.
- $O_{(b)}^a$ (or $Z_{(b)}^a$) denotes the b -th bit ($b=0$ is the least significant bit or lsb) of

the second output word generated at round a when key_1 (or key_2) is used. We do not use the first output word anywhere in our analysis.

- P_1^a, Y_1^a and s_1^a are the inputs to the PRBG at round a when key_1 is used. It is easy to see that when this convention is followed the O^a takes a simple form: $O^a = (s \oplus Y^a[-1]) + Y^a[P^a[208]]$. The same applies to key_2 .
- $P_1^a[b], Y_1^a[b]$ denote the b -th elements of arrays P_1^a and Y_1^a respectively, when key_1 is used. The same applies to key_2 .
- $P_1^a[b]_{(i)}, Y_1^a[b]_{(i)}$ denote the i -th bits of elements $P_1^a[b]$ and $Y_1^a[b]$ respectively, when key_1 is used. The same applies to key_2 .
- The operators ‘+’, ‘-’ and ‘ \oplus ’ denote addition modulo 2^{32} , subtraction modulo 2^{32} and bitwise exclusive-or respectively, \cap denotes set intersection and \cup denotes set union.

2.2 Sekar et al.'s Attacks on Py-family of Stream Ciphers at Indocrypt 2007

In paper [Sekar, 07d], Sekar, Paul and Preneel presented related-key distinguishing attacks on TPpy, TPy, Ppy and Py, whose data complexity is $2^{193.7}$. They show that, when used with the identical IVs of 16 bytes each, if two long keys key_1 and key_2 of 256 bytes each, are related in the following manner,

- C1. $key_1[16] \oplus key_2[16] = 1$,
- C2. $key_1[17] \neq key_2[17]$ and
- C3. $key_1[i] = key_2[i], \forall i \notin \{16, 17\}$

Then, they showed that the relation between two keys (C1-C3) can be traced through various parts of the Py-family of stream ciphers (i.e., TPpy, TPy, Ppy and Py). That is, using the above relation, they exploited the weaknesses of the key setup algorithms of Py-family of stream ciphers, and propagated through the IV setup algorithms and finally induced biases in the keystream outputs. Here, the process of trace is skipped, and we consider only the result of this process. Let D denote the event $Y_1[i] = Y_2[i]$ (where $-3 \leq i \leq 12$) after IV setup. Then we have a proposition from [Sekar, 07d].

Proposition 1 [Sekar, 07d]. Under the relation between the keys (C1-C3), the event D after key setup and IV setup occurs with probability

$$\Pr(D) = 2^{-28.4} \cdot \left(\frac{255}{256}\right)^{16} = 2^{-28.5}$$

As shown in paper [Sekar, 07d], in the first 17 rounds of IV setup part-2 (see Algorithm 2 of Appendix A), the differences in key [16] and key [17] between key_1 and key_2 causes the internal state s to be different, and then causes EIV to be different in the following round and hence $P_1 \neq P_2$. In the subsequent rounds, the mixing becomes more random. Finally, at the end of IV setup, $Y_1[i] = Y_2[i]$ (where $-3 \leq i \leq 12$), $P_1 \neq P_2$, $s_1 \neq s_2$ and $Y_1[i] \neq Y_2[i]$ (where $13 \leq i \leq 256$). Thus, the internal state P , s and $Y[i]$ (where $13 \leq i \leq 256$) after IV setup can be considered to be uniformly distributed and independent.

After the process of trace, they finally induced biases in the least significant bit of the outputs at the 1st and the 3rd rounds. That is,

$$\Pr(O_{(0)}^1 \oplus O_{(0)}^3 \oplus Z_{(0)}^1 \oplus Z_{(0)}^3 = 0) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2^{96.4}} \right)$$

Therefore, using Theorem 6 of [Baigneres, 04], they showed that the number of samples required to establish an optimal distinguisher with advantage greater than 0.5 is $2^{193.7}$.

3 Related-key Distinguishing Attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64

In this section, we will present our related-key distinguishing attacks on RCR-64 and RCR-32 stream ciphers. The key/IV setup algorithms of RCR-64 and RCR-32 are identical with those of TPy and TPpy. The round function of RCR-64 and RCR-32 are also very similar to those of the TPy and TPpy. The only changes in the round function are that: the variables rotation of the quantity s is replaced by a constant rotation of 19. Single round of RCR-64 and RCR-32 are shown in algorithm 4 of Appendix B.

Since the first 32-bit keystream word of RF_3 at each round is skipped, thus, they consider only the round function RF_3 of Algorithm 4 (see Appendix B). Let s_1^i, P_1^i, Y_1^i (or s_2^i, P_2^i, Y_2^i) denote the internal state s, P and Y after IV setup when key_1 (or key_2) is used. At the end of any round $i(i \geq 1)$, the internal state is updated to $s_1^{i+1}, P_1^{i+1}, Y_1^{i+1}$ (or $s_2^{i+1}, P_2^{i+1}, Y_2^{i+1}$) when key_1 (or key_2) is used. In our attacks on RCR-64 and RCR-32, we will induce biases in the outputs at the 1st and the 2nd rounds, not 1st and the 3rd rounds. The formulas for the least significant bit of the outputs generated at rounds 1 and 2 when key_1 (the output words are denoted by O) and key_2 (the output words are denoted by Z) are used are given below.

$$O_{(0)}^1 = s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus Y_1^1[-1]_{(0)} \oplus Y_1^1[P_1^2[208]]_{(0)} \tag{1}$$

$$O_{(0)}^2 = s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus Y_1^2[-1]_{(0)} \oplus Y_1^2[P_1^3[208]]_{(0)} \tag{2}$$

$$Z_{(0)}^1 = s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus Y_2^1[-1]_{(0)} \oplus Y_2^1[P_2^2[208]]_{(0)} \tag{3}$$

$$Z_{(0)}^2 = s_{2(0)}^3 \oplus Y_2^2[-1]_{(0)} \oplus Y_2^2[P_2^3[208]]_{(0)} \tag{4}$$

Recall the round function RF_3 of Algorithm 3. When the event D occurs, $Y_1^1[-1] = Y_2^1[-1]$ and $Y_1^2[-1] = Y_2^2[-1]$ are always satisfied. Thus,

$$Y_1^1[-1] = Y_2^1[-1] \Rightarrow Y_1^1[-1]_{(0)} = Y_2^1[-1]_{(0)}$$

$$Y_1^2[-1] = Y_2^2[-1] \Rightarrow Y_1^2[-1]_{(0)} = Y_2^2[-1]_{(0)}$$

Let C_1, C_2, C_3 and C_4 denote $Y_1^1[P_1^2[208]]_{(0)}, Y_1^2[P_1^3[208]]_{(0)}, Y_2^1[P_2^2[208]]_{(0)}$ and $Y_2^2[P_2^3[208]]_{(0)}$, respectively. In order to make $C_1 \oplus C_2 \oplus C_3 \oplus C_4 = 0$ (denoted by event G) to be satisfied with a high probability, some conditions on the elements of P_1 and P_2 should be simultaneously satisfied. Concluded from a large number of experiments, it is determined that when the two conditions $P_1^2[208] = P_1^3[208] + 1$ (denoted by event U_1) and $P_2^2[208] = P_2^3[208] + 1$ (denoted by event U_2) are

simultaneously satisfied, the probability that the event G occurs is quite close to 1. Running simulation, it is determined that

$$\Pr(G) = \Pr(U_1 \cap U_2) \approx 2^{-8} \cdot 2^{-8} = 2^{-16}$$

The formulas for s_1^3 and s_2^3 is given below:

$$s_1^3 = RTOTL32(s_1^2 + Y_1^2[P_1^3[72]] - Y_1^2[P_1^3[239]], 19) \quad (5)$$

$$s_2^3 = RTOTL32(s_2^2 + Y_2^2[P_2^3[72]] - Y_2^2[P_2^3[239]], 19) \quad (6)$$

Let $c_1 = Y_1^2[P_1^3[72]] - Y_1^2[P_1^3[239]]$ and $c_2 = Y_2^2[P_2^3[72]] - Y_2^2[P_2^3[239]]$. Let δ and γ represent the carry bits from the additions in the equations (5) and (6), respectively. Thus, we know $s_1^2 + c_1 = s_1^2 \oplus c_1 \oplus \delta$ and $s_2^2 + c_2 = s_2^2 \oplus c_2 \oplus \gamma$.

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} & s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3 \\ &= s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(19)}^2 \oplus c_{1(19)} \oplus \delta_{(19)} \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(19)}^2 \oplus c_{2(19)} \oplus \gamma_{(19)} \\ &= s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(19)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(19)}^2 \oplus c_{1(19)} \oplus c_{2(19)} \oplus \delta_{(19)} \oplus \gamma_{(19)} \end{aligned}$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{(19)} &= s_{1(18)}^2 c_{1(18)} \oplus \delta_{(18)} s_{1(18)}^2 \oplus \delta_{(18)} c_{1(18)} \\ \gamma_{(19)} &= s_{2(18)}^2 c_{2(18)} \oplus \gamma_{(18)} s_{2(18)}^2 \oplus \gamma_{(18)} c_{2(18)} \end{aligned}$$

We now state the following proposition.

Proposition 2. $s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3 = 0$ when the following conditions are simultaneously satisfied.

1. $s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(19)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(19)}^2 \oplus \delta_{(19)} \oplus \gamma_{(19)} = 0$ (event E_1)

2. $P_1^3[72] = P_2^3[72] = a \in \{-3, -2, \dots, 11\}$,

$$P_1^3[239] = P_2^3[239] = b \in \{-3, -2, \dots, 11\} \text{ and } b \neq a \text{ (event } E_2)$$

Proof. Recall the round function RF_3 of Algorithm 4.

Since it has $Y_1[i] = Y_2[i]$ (where $-3 \leq i \leq 12$) at the end of IV setup, and then the event E_2 implies $Y_1^2[P_1^3[72]] = Y_2^2[P_2^3[72]]$ and $Y_1^2[P_1^3[239]] = Y_2^2[P_2^3[239]]$. That is, $c_1 = c_2 \Rightarrow c_{1(19)} = c_{2(19)}$.

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} & s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3 \\ &= s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(19)}^2 \oplus c_{1(19)} \oplus \delta_{(19)} \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(19)}^2 \oplus c_{2(19)} \oplus \gamma_{(19)} \\ &= s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(19)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(19)}^2 \oplus \delta_{(19)} \oplus \gamma_{(19)} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, condition 1 and condition 2 together imply $s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3 = 0$.

This completes the proof. \square

Since the internal state P , s and $Y[i]$ (where $13 \leq i \leq 256$) after IV setup can be considered to be uniformly distributed and independent, and then we know

$$\Pr(E_1) \approx 2^{-1} \text{ and } \Pr(E_2) \approx 2^{-8} \cdot \frac{15}{256} \cdot 2^{-8} \cdot \frac{14}{256} = 2^{-23.7}.$$

The two events E_1 and E_2 are assumed to be independent to facilitate calculation of bias. The actual value without independence assumption is in fact more, making the attack marginally stronger. Let E denote the event $E_1 \cap E_2$. Hence,

$$\Pr(E) = \Pr(E_1 \cap E_2) \approx \Pr(E_1) \cdot \Pr(E_2) = 2^{-24.7}.$$

Therefore, from Proposition 1 and equations (1-4), we observe that $O_{(0)}^1 \oplus O_{(0)}^2 \oplus Z_{(0)}^1 \oplus Z_{(0)}^2 = 0$ holds when the following events simultaneously occur.

D, G and E .

In the following, we calculate the probability that $O_{(0)}^1 \oplus O_{(0)}^2 \oplus Z_{(0)}^1 \oplus Z_{(0)}^2 = 0$ is satisfied. Let L denote the event $(D \cap G \cap E)$. Thus,

$$\Pr(L) \approx \Pr(D) \cdot \Pr(G) \cdot \Pr(E) = 2^{-28.5} \cdot 2^{-16} \cdot 2^{-24.7} = 2^{-69.2}$$

Assuming randomness of the outputs when event L does not occur, we have

$$\Pr(O_{(0)}^1 \oplus O_{(0)}^2 \oplus Z_{(0)}^1 \oplus Z_{(0)}^2 = 0) = 2^{-69.2} \cdot 1 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (1 - 2^{-69.2}) = \frac{1}{2} (1 + 2^{-69.2})$$

To compute the number of samples required to establish an optimal distinguisher with advantage greater than 0.5, we use the following equation from [Paul, 06, Baigneres, 04].

$$N = 0.4624 \cdot \frac{1}{p^2}$$

Here, $p = 2^{-70.2}$. Therefore, the number of samples is $2^{139.3}$.

Therefore, the number of samples required for our distinguishing attack is $2^{139.3}$.

4 Improved Related-key Distinguishing Attacks on Py-family Stream Ciphers

In this section, we will apply our related-key attacks on Py-family of stream ciphers (i.e., TPpy, TPy, Ppy and Py) to improve the attacks presented by Sekar et al.

Since the first 32-bit keystream word of RF_1 at each round is skipped, thus, we consider only the round function RF_1 of Algorithm 3 (see Appendix A).

The formulas for s_1^3 and s_2^3 is given below:

$$s_1^3 = RTOTL32(s_1^2 + Y_1^2[P_1^3[72]] - Y_1^2[P_1^3[239]], (P_1^3[116] + 18) \bmod 32) \quad (7)$$

$$s_2^3 = RTOTL32(s_2^2 + Y_2^2[P_2^3[72]] - Y_2^2[P_2^3[239]], (P_2^3[116] + 18) \bmod 32) \quad (8)$$

Let $e_1 = Y_1^2[P_1^3[72]] - Y_1^2[P_1^3[239]]$, $e_2 = Y_2^2[P_2^3[72]] - Y_2^2[P_2^3[239]]$, $d_1 = (P_1^3[116] + 18) \bmod 32$ and $d_2 = (P_2^3[116] + 18) \bmod 32$. Let β and ε represent the carry bits from the additions in the equations (7) and (8), respectively. Thus, we know $s_1^2 + e_1 = s_1^2 \oplus e_1 \oplus \beta$ and $s_2^2 + e_2 = s_2^2 \oplus e_2 \oplus \varepsilon$. Without loss of generality, set lsb of β and ε (denoted by $\beta_{(0)}$ and $\varepsilon_{(0)}$) be 0.

Therefore,

$$s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(d_1)}^2 \oplus e_{1(d_1)} \oplus \beta_{(d_1)} \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(d_2)}^2 \oplus e_{2(d_2)} \oplus \varepsilon_{(d_2)} \\
&= s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(d_1)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(d_2)}^2 \oplus e_{1(d_1)} \oplus e_{2(d_2)} \oplus \beta_{(d_1)} \oplus \varepsilon_{(d_2)}
\end{aligned}$$

Where

$$\beta_{(d_1)} = \begin{cases} 0, & d_1 = 0 \\ s_{1(d_1-1)}^2 e_{1(d_1-1)} \oplus \beta_{(d_1-1)} s_{1(d_1-1)}^2 \oplus \beta_{(d_1-1)} e_{1(d_1-1)}, & 1 \leq d_1 \leq 31 \end{cases}$$

$$\varepsilon_{(d_2)} = \begin{cases} 0, & d_2 = 0 \\ s_{1(d_2-1)}^2 e_{1(d_2-1)} \oplus \varepsilon_{(d_2-1)} s_{1(d_2-1)}^2 \oplus \varepsilon_{(d_2-1)} e_{1(d_2-1)}, & 1 \leq d_2 \leq 31 \end{cases}$$

Similarly, we now state the following proposition.

Proposition 2. $s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3 = 0$ when the following conditions are simultaneously satisfied.

1. $d_1 = d_2$ (event F_1)
2. $s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(d_1)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(d_2)}^2 \oplus \beta_{(d_1)} \oplus \varepsilon_{(d_2)} = 0$ (event F_2)
3. $P_1^3[72] = P_2^3[72] = a \in \{-3, -2, \dots, 11\}$,
 $P_1^3[239] = P_2^3[239] = b \in \{-3, -2, \dots, 11\}$ and $b \neq a$ (event F_3)

Proof. Recall the round function RF_3 of Algorithm 4.

Since it has $Y_1[i] = Y_2[i]$ (where $-3 \leq i \leq 12$) at the end of IV setup, and then the condition F_3 implies $Y_1^2[P_1^3[72]] - Y_1^2[P_1^3[239]] = Y_2^2[P_2^3[72]] - Y_2^2[P_2^3[239]]$. Conditions F_1 and F_3 together imply $e_{1(d_1)} \oplus e_{2(d_2)} = 0$.

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
& s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3 \\
&= s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(d_1)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(d_2)}^2 \oplus c_{1(d_1)} \oplus c_{2(d_2)} \oplus \delta_{(d_1)} \oplus \gamma_{(d_2)} \\
&= s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(d_1)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(d_2)}^2 \oplus \delta_{(d_1)} \oplus \gamma_{(d_2)}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, condition 1, condition 2 and condition 3 together imply $s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3 = 0$.

This completes the proof. \square

Since the internal state P , s and $Y[i]$ (where $13 \leq i \leq 256$) after IV setup can be considered to be uniformly distributed and independent, and then we know

$$\Pr(F_1) \approx 2^{-5}, \Pr(F_2) \approx 2^{-1} \text{ and } \Pr(F_3) \approx 2^{-8} \cdot \frac{15}{256} \cdot 2^{-8} \cdot \frac{14}{256} = 2^{-23.7}.$$

Let F denote the event $F_1 \cap F_2 \cap F_3$. Hence,

$$\Pr(F) = \Pr(F_1 \cap F_2 \cap F_3) \approx \Pr(F_1) \cdot \Pr(F_2) \cdot \Pr(F_3) = 2^{-29.7}.$$

Therefore, we observe that $O_{(0)}^1 \oplus O_{(0)}^2 \oplus Z_{(0)}^1 \oplus Z_{(0)}^2 = 0$ holds when the following events simultaneously occur.

D , G and F .

Let Q denote the event $(D \cap G \cap F)$. Then, we get

$$\Pr(Q) \approx \Pr(D) \cdot \Pr(G) \cdot \Pr(F) = 2^{-28.5} \cdot 2^{-16} \cdot 2^{-29.7} = 2^{-74.2}$$

Assuming randomness of the outputs when event Q does not occur, we have

$$\Pr(O_{(0)}^1 \oplus O_{(0)}^2 \oplus Z_{(0)}^1 \oplus Z_{(0)}^2 = 0) = 2^{-74.2} \cdot 1 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot (1 - 2^{-74.2}) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + 2^{-74.2})$$

To compute the number of samples required to establish an optimal distinguisher with advantage greater than 0.5, we use the following equation from [Paul, 06, Baigneres, 04].

$$N = 0.4624 \cdot \frac{1}{p^2}$$

Here, $p = 2^{-75.2}$. Therefore, the number of samples is $2^{149.3}$. Compared with paper [Sekar, 07d], in our related-key attacks on Py-family of stream ciphers, we induce biases in the outputs at the 1st and the 2nd rounds, not 1st and the 3rd rounds. We make a more accurate evaluation on the probability that $s_{1(0)}^2 \oplus s_{1(0)}^3 \oplus s_{2(0)}^2 \oplus s_{2(0)}^3 = 0$ holds. Hence, our attacks improve the attacks proposed in [Sekar, 07d] obviously in terms of data complexity.

5 New Stream Ciphers: TRCR-32 and TRCR-64

5.1 Comparison of Our Results with Previous Attacks

The stream cipher TPpy has been designed by Biham and Seberry in January 2007 as the strongest member of the Py-family stream ciphers. At Indocrypt 2007, Sekar, Paul and Preneel showed related-key weaknesses in the Py-family of stream ciphers including the strongest member TPpy. Furthermore, they modified the stream ciphers TPpy and TPy to generate two fast ciphers, namely RCR-32 and RCR-64, in an attempt to rule out all the attacks against the Py-family of stream ciphers. So far there exist no attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64.

Attacks	Py6	Py	Ppy	TPy6	TPy	TPpy	RCR-32	RCR-64
[Paul, 06]	X	$2^{89.2}$	X	X	$2^{89.2}$	X	X	X
[Crowley, 06]	X	2^{72}	X	X	2^{72}	X	X	X
[Wu, 07]	$< 2^{24}$	2^{24}	2^{24}	X	X	X	X	X
[Isobe, 06]	$< 2^{24}$	2^{24}	2^{24}	X	X	X	X	X
[Paul, 06]	$2^{68.6}$	X	X	$2^{68.6}$	X	X	X	X
[Sekar, 07a]	X	2^{281}	2^{281}	X	2^{281}	2^{281}	X	X
[Sekar, 07b]	X	$2^{268.6}$	X	X	$2^{268.6}$	X	X	X
[Sekar, 07c]	$2^{224.6}$	X	X	$2^{224.6}$	X	X	X	X
[Tsunoo, 07]	X	X	X	X	X	2^{199}	X	X
[Sekar, 07d]	X	$2^{193.7}$	$2^{193.7}$	X	$2^{193.7}$	$2^{193.7}$	X	X
Related key(this paper)	X	$2^{149.3}$	$2^{149.3}$	X	$2^{149.3}$	$2^{149.3}$	$2^{139.3}$	$2^{139.3}$

Table 2: Comparison of our results with previous attacks on Py-family of stream ciphers (Note: 'X' denotes that the attack does not work.)

In Section 3 and 4, we show that the related-key weaknesses can be still used to construct related-key distinguishing attacks on all Py-family of stream ciphers including the modified versions RCR-32 and RCR-64. Under related keys, we show distinguishing attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64 with data complexity $2^{139.3}$ and advantage greater than 0.5. We also show that the data complexity of the distinguishing attacks on Py-family of stream ciphers proposed by Sekar et al. can be reduced from $2^{193.7}$ to $2^{149.3}$. These results constitute the best attacks on the strongest members of the Py-family of stream ciphers Tppy, RCR-32 and RCR-64. It is shown that the above attacks also work on the other members TPy, Ppy and Py.

Table 3 summarizes the attacks on Py-family of stream ciphers. Compared with previous attacks, our results constitute the best attacks on the strongest members of the Py-family of stream cipher Tppy. We also introduce the first attack on RCR-32 and RCR-64, which shows the modifications made by Sekar, Paul and Preneel to generate RCR-32 and RCR-64 are not reasonable. In the next subsection, we will present our modifications to improve all Py-family of stream ciphers.

5.2 New Proposal for Key Setup Algorithm

In [Sekar, 07d], Sekar, Paul and Preneel showed related-key weaknesses in the Py-family of stream ciphers, and then made simple modifications to the ciphers Tppy and TPy to build RCR-32 and RCR-64 respectively. In their modified designs, the key scheduling algorithms of RCR-32 and RCR-64 are identical with those of Tppy and TPy. They modified the round function of Tppy and TPy to build RCR-32 and RCR-64 respectively. Our attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64 show their modifications are not reasonable. In this subsection, we propose a new proposal for key setup algorithm which is similar to the original.

Our attacks can succeed mainly because of the weaknesses of the key setup algorithms of Py-family of stream ciphers. Hence, modifying the key setup algorithm is a more reasonable choice. According to Proposition 1, under the relation between the keys $(C1-C3)$, the event D after key setup and IV setup occurs with probability $2^{-28.5}$. This shows the initialization of Py-family of stream ciphers is quite bad in terms of the completeness property. Recall the key setup algorithm (see Algorithm 1 of Appendix A). Each element of array Y has been updated only once in key setup algorithm, which makes the event D after key setup and IV setup occur with high probability.

In this subsection, we propose two new stream ciphers, TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 derived from RCR-32 and RCR-64, which are shown to be secure against all the existing attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64. The IV setup algorithms and round functions of TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 are identical with those of RCR-32 and RCR-64. The only changes in the key setup algorithms are that: the array Y is updated twice not once. The new proposal for key setup algorithm of all Py-family of stream ciphers is shown in Algorithm 5.

Algorithm 5 Key Setup Algorithm of TRCR-32 and TRCR-64

```

Require: A key, an IV and an initial permutation
Ensure: An array Y [-3, . . . , 256] and a 32-bit variable s
keysizeb = size of key in bytes;
ivsizeb = size of IV in bytes;
YMININD=-3;
YMAXIND=256;
s = internal_permutation[keysizeb-1];
s = (s<<8) | internal_permutation[(s^(ivsizeb-1))&0xFF];
s = (s<<8) | internal_permutation[(s^key[0])&0xFF];
s = (s<<8) | internal_permutation[(s^key[keysizeb-1])&0xFF];
for(j=0; j<keysizeb; j++) /* Part-1*/
{
    s = s + key[j];
    s0 = internal_permutation[s&0xFF];
    s = ROTL32(s, 8) ^ (u32)s0;
}
/* Tweak - Initialize the array Y */
for(i=YMININD, j=0; i<=YMAXIND; i++) /* Part-2*/
{
    s = s + key[j];
    s0 = internal_permutation[s&0xFF];
    Y(i) = s = ROTL32(s, 8) ^ (u32)s0;
    j = j+1 mod keysizeb;
}
/* Tweak - Update the array Y */
for(i=YMAXIND, j= YMININD; i>=YMININD; i--) /* Part-3*/
{
    s = s + Y[j];
    s0 = internal_permutation[s&0xFF];
    Y(i) = s = ROTL32(s, 8) ^ (u32)s0;
    j++;
}

```

5.3 Security Analysis

In this section we justify how the new stream ciphers TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 should be able to resist several common attacks against array-based stream ciphers.

- (i) *Resistance to Distinguishing Attacks, Differential attacks, Algebraic attacks and Guess-and-Determine Attacks:* Since the IV setup algorithms and round functions of TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 are identical with those of RCR-32 and RCR-64, these attacks are no longer applicable in new stream ciphers.
- (ii) *Resistance to Related-key attacks [Sekar, 07d, this paper]:* When tracing the relation between two keys (C1-C3) through various parts of the Py-family of stream ciphers, we find that the internal state (i.e., P, Y and s) are uniformly distributed at random after key/IV setup algorithms. At the end of Part-2 of

Algorithm 5, we have $P_1 = P_2$, $s_1 = s_2$ and $Y_1[i] = Y_2[i]$ (where $i \neq 13$). In the Part-3 of Algorithm 5, we use one element of array Y to update the other element of array Y, instead of the key. The difference in arrays Y_1 and Y_2 (i.e., $Y_1[13] \neq Y_2[13]$) causes the internal state s to be different, and then causes the array Y to be different. In the subsequent rounds of IV setup algorithm, the mixing becomes more random. Finally, at the end of IV setup, $Y_1 \neq Y_2$, $P_1 \neq P_2$ and $s_1 \neq s_2$. Hence, the new stream ciphers TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 have much better completeness properties than the original RCR-32 and RCR-64 stream ciphers, and then the internal state P , s and Y after IV setup algorithm can be considered to be uniformly distributed and independent. Therefore, the outputs generated in the keystream generation algorithm are not expected to be correlated. Hence, the new stream ciphers TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 are expected to be free from any correlations between the outputs.

Based on our security analysis, we conjecture that no attacks lower than brute force are possible on TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 stream ciphers.

6 Conclusions

In this paper, we show that the related-key weaknesses can be still used to construct related-key distinguishing attacks on all Py-family of stream ciphers including the modified versions RCR-32 and RCR-64. Under related keys, we show distinguishing attacks on RCR-32 and RCR-64 with data complexity $2^{139.3}$ and advantage greater than 0.5. We also show that the data complexity of the distinguishing attacks on Py-family of stream ciphers proposed by Sekar et al. can be reduced from $2^{193.7}$ to $2^{149.3}$. These results constitute the best attacks on the strongest members of the Py-family of stream ciphers Tpyy, RCR-32 and RCR-64. By modifying the key setup algorithm, we propose two new stream ciphers TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 which are derived from RCR-32 and RCR-64 respectively. Based on our security analysis, we conjecture that no attacks lower than brute force are possible on TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 stream ciphers.

We hope our results can be helpful in evaluating the security of Py-family stream ciphers against related-key distinguishing attacks and we look forward to further work in evaluating TRCR-32 and TRCR-64 against other kinds of cryptanalytic attacks.

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Appendix A Various Parts of Py-family of Stream Ciphers

Algorithm 1 Key setup: KS

Require: A key, an IV and an *initial permutation*

Ensure: An array Y [-3, . . . , 256] and a 32-bit variable s

keysizeb = size of key in bytes;

ivsizeb = size of IV in bytes;

YMININD=-3;

YMAXIND=256;

$s = \text{internal_permutation}[\text{keysizeb}-1];$

$s = (s \ll 8) \mid \text{internal_permutation}[(s \wedge (\text{ivsizeb}-1)) \& 0\text{xFF}];$

$s = (s \ll 8) \mid \text{internal_permutation}[(s \wedge \text{key}[0]) \& 0\text{xFF}];$

$s = (s \ll 8) \mid \text{internal_permutation}[(s \wedge \text{key}[\text{keysizeb}-1]) \& 0\text{xFF}];$

for(j=0; j<keysizeb; j++)

{

$s = s + \text{key}[j];$

$s0 = \text{internal_permutation}[s \& 0\text{xFF}];$

$s = \text{ROTL32}(s, 8) \wedge (\text{u32})s0;$

}

/* Again */

for(j=0; j<keysizeb; j++)

{

$s = s + \text{key}[j];$

$s0 = \text{internal_permutation}[s \& 0\text{xFF}];$

$s \wedge= \text{ROTL32}(s, 8) + (\text{u32})s0;$

}

/* Initialize the array Y */

for(i=YMININD, j=0; i<=YMAXIND; i++)

{

$s = s + \text{key}[j];$

$s0 = \text{internal_permutation}[s \& 0\text{xFF}];$

$Y(i) = s = \text{ROTL32}(s, 8) \wedge (\text{u32})s0;$

$j = j+1 \text{ mod } \text{keysizeb};$

}

Algorithm 2 The IV setup algorithms of IVS_1 and IVS_2 - initialization of P and EIV

Require: The Y , the s from the key setup algorithm and the IV
Ensure: Rolling arrays $P[0, \dots, 255]$, $EIV[0, \dots, ivsizeb - 1]$, the variable s

```

/* Create an initial permutation */
u8 v= iv[0] ^ ((Y(0)>>16)&0xFF);
u8 d=(iv[1 mod ivsizeb] ^ ((Y(1)>>16)&0xFF))|1;
for(i=0; i<256; i++)
{
    P(i)=internal_permutation[v];
    v+=d;
}
/* Now P is a permutation */
/* Initialize s */
s = ((u32)v<<24) ^ ((u32)d<<16) ^ ((u32)P(254)<<8) ^ ((u32)P(255));
s ^= Y(YMININD)+Y(YMAXIND);
for(i=0; i<ivsizeb; i++)
{
    s = s + iv[i] + Y(YMININD+i);
    u8 s0 = P(s&0xFF);
    EIV(i) = s0;
    s = ROTL32(s, 8) ^ (u32)s0;
}
/* Again, but with the last words of Y, and update EIV */
for(i=0; i<ivsizeb; i++)
{
    s = s + iv[i] + Y(YMAXIND-i);
    /*s = s + EIV((i+ivsizeb-1)mod ivsizeb) + Y(YMAXIND-i); for IVS1.*/
    u8 s0 = P(s&0xFF);
    EIV(i) += s0;
    s = ROTL32(s, 8) ^ (u32)s0;
}

for(i=0; i<260; i++) //IV setup part-2
{
    u32 x0 = EIV(0) = EIV(0) ^ (s&0xFF);
    rotate(EIV);
    swap(P(0), P(x0));
    rotate(P);
    Y(YMININD)=s=(s ^ Y(YMININD))+Y(x0);
    /*s=ROTL32(s,8)+Y(YMAXIND);Y(YMININD)+=s^Y(x0); for IVS1.*/
    rotate(Y);
}
s=s+Y(26)+Y(153)+Y(208);
if(s==0)
    s=(keysizeb*8)+((ivsizeb*8)<<16)+0x87654321;

```

Algorithm 3 Round functions: RF_1 and RF_2

Require: $Y[-3, \dots, 256]$, $P[0, \dots, 255]$, a 32-bit variable s **Ensure:** 32-bit random output (for RF_1) or 64-bit random output (for RF_2)

/*Update and rotate P*/

swap ($P[0]$, $P[Y[185]\&255]$);rotate (P);

/* Update s*/

 $s+ = Y[P[72]] - Y[P[239]]$; $s = \text{ROTL32}(s, ((P[116] + 18)\&31))$;

/* Output 4 or 8 bytes (least significant byte first)*/

output ($(\text{ROTL32}(s, 25) \square Y[256]) + Y[P[26]]$);/* This step is skipped for RF_1 .*/output ($((s \square Y[-1]) + Y[P[208]])$);

/* Update and rotate Y */

 $Y[-3] = (\text{ROTL32}(s, 14) \square Y[-3]) + Y[P[153]]$;rotate(Y);

Appendix B Round Function of RCR-32 and RCR-64

Algorithm 4 Round functions of RCR-32 and RCR-64: RF_3 and RF_4

Require: $Y[-3, \dots, 256]$, $P[0, \dots, 255]$, a 32-bit variable s **Ensure:** 64-bit random output (for RCR-64) or 32-bit random output (for RCR-32)

/*Update and rotate P*/

swap ($P[0]$, $P[Y[185]\&255]$);rotate (P);

/* Update s*/

 $s+ = Y[P[72]] - Y[P[239]]$; $s = \text{ROTL32}(s, 19)$; /*Tweak - the variable s undergoes a constant, non-zero rotation ($c = 19$).*/

/* Output 4 or 8 bytes (the least significant byte first)*/

output ($(\text{ROTL32}(s, 25) \square Y[256]) + Y[P[26]]$);/* This step is skipped for RF_3 .*/output ($((s \square Y[-1]) + Y[P[208]])$);

/* Update and rotate Y */

 $Y[-3] = (\text{ROTL32}(s, 14) \square Y[-3]) + Y[P[153]]$;rotate(Y);
